

PROVINCIAL, DISTRICT AND TOURISM POLICIES CITIES IN BALI: DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OVERVIEW REGIONAL TOURISM

I PUTU ANOM¹ and IDA AYU SURYASIH²

^{1,2} Tourism Faculty, Udayana University, Indonesia.

Email: ¹putuanom@unud.ac.id, ²idaayusuryasih@unud.ac.id

Abstract

Tourism policy is an important area to study because of its practical and theoretical importance. The different tourism policies created by different regions are one of the main factors for the existence and development of tourism, along with the natural and anthropogenic resources of a particular destination. Tourism policy research has practical significance because travel requires government cooperation, for example, bilateral airline negotiations, decisions about the provision of facilities and services, interactions with other sectors, use of publicly 'owned' resources such as national parks as attractions, issuance of tourist visas. And marketing funding for certain destinations. This is in addition to the fact that many tourist village policies have been implemented and synchronization with follow-up programs has been running in each district/city. A number of suggestions that need to be conveyed are to the provincial/regency and city governments to focus more on what is stipulated in the tourism village policy. Programs developed to be more focused on achieving the vision and mission of regional tourism development. To the tourist village, to better coordinate the tourist village development program with various parties so that the objectives of establishing a tourist village can be realized. This condition is based on the large number of tourist villages that have not taken further action after being designated as tourist villages.

1. INTRODUCTION

The government has control over how people behave, the administration of social relations, international affairs, border security, social and community development. This government involvement is widespread and can occur at national, provincial and local levels and there is an opinion that 'good' policy requires the involvement of all three (Kerr, 2003). Reasons for government involvement and policy formulation include market failures, governments seeking to understand and reduce the cultural, social and environmental impacts of tourism, tourism's use of public goods, and the spatial nature of tourism requiring land use planning (Kerr, 2003).

Governments are interested in tourism because of its enormous economic, social and environmental impacts, as tourism is generally considered to contribute to the world economy with consequent effects on the communities and natural environments with which it interacts. Perhaps tourism policy would not be so important if these economic benefits were only available to certain regions or tourism was a closed system where the potential for additional impacts and damage from external shocks, crises and disasters was smaller. On the other hand, most governments have involvement in tourism, although the existence of formally stated and publicly accessible national tourism policies is by no means universal (Baum, 1994).

Government tourism policy may also be indirect, where government actions influence tourism as a by-product of an interest in some related field; or direct where the government actively tries to influence tourism or some aspect of tourism in achieving policy goals (Airey, 1983). In general, governments consider tourism as a source of economic development, increasing its

priority especially for developing countries. Since the rapid development of the tourism industry, there has been disharmony between the driving sectors of Bali's economy, namely creative economy tourism, industry, agriculture and other sectors. One case, when the tourism sector promises fast and multiple results, the agricultural sector is actually neglected.

Bali, with its relatively narrow territory, certainly has limited resource carrying capacity. With a narrow area, dense population and development across sectors, especially the agricultural sector and the tourism sector, which is very unequal, this causes land conversion to occur which cannot be avoided. This research tries to construct the policies taken by regional governments (Provincial, Regency and City) in Bali and synergize tourism with other sectors.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The introduction of choice and the idea that public policy involves choices about whether to develop policies and what types of policy choices need to be made suggests that 'public policy is more than what governments do'. Tourism policy making is seen by Hall (2000) as first and foremost a political activity, influenced by the economic, social and cultural characteristics of a particular society, and by the formal structure of government and other features. Of the local political system. Policy involves considering 'political debates about what the agenda is, what the problem is, who is involved or affected, and alternative actions to address the problem' (Dredge & Jenkins, 2007).

This debate can go beyond governments and include 'policy-making tourism organizations (national tourism organizations, information offices, consumer associations) and the tourism industry (hotels, restaurants, tour operators, travel agents); even pressure groups may have a voice in the policy-making process' (VanDoorn, 1982). The choice between different development strategies illustrates the importance of ideology in determining policy choices; Ideological beliefs provide the 'guiding principles that set the tone and pace of development'. Thus 'development theories, policies, plans and strategies consciously or unconsciously express preferred ideas about what development is and these preferences, in turn, reflect values' and ideologies (Sharpley & Telfer, 2002).

Based on early tourism 'failures' in developing countries and the lessons learned, a number of other development theories developed, and at one time may have been dominant or determined. Azcairate (2006) lists these as modernization, dependency theory, human development and post-development. Harrison and Schipani (2007) provide a historical sequence of change from a 'simple modernization model', to the reaction evident in dependency theory, to alternative tourism, the inclusion of social and environmental protection, and community-based approaches (Hall, 2007).

A similar sequence is found in Jafari's (1989) four platforms - (advocacy, warning, adaptation and knowledge-based) reflecting ideological and policy changes (Swain, et al., 1999). Weaver (2001) has summarized the relationship between tourism platforms, paradigm shifts, tourism structures and the status of ecotourism in Western societies. With successive changes in development paradigms, the focus of tourism policy has shifted from pure promotion, to

product development, to maintaining competitiveness (Fayos-Sola, 1992a). More recently, post-development studies have understood development as a global discourse contested by local 'Others' although this discourse can be considered a two-way process mediated by powerful local actors (Azcairate, 2006).

3. METHODOLOGY

Approaches to analyzing public policy have been grouped into four types; rational choice, socio-economics, institutions and networks. The rational choice or scientific approach focuses on providing factual knowledge and analysis rather than an intrinsically political view, and in the same way, each approach is based on a particular view of the world and how it works, and combines theories and concepts, but which may overlap with other approaches.

4. RESULTS

The rapid development of tourism in Bali Province has contributed in the form of job creation and investment. On the other hand, it has resulted in high migration to the island of Bali, especially in the southern Bali region, both from the Bali region and outside the Bali region.

The development of tourism, which has resulted in various advances in various areas of life, on the other hand has also given rise to various development problems, which have direct implications for carrying capacity and carrying capacity, such as: increasing demand for land, both for settlements and tourism activities; the increase and rapid conversion of agricultural land; reduced regional vegetation cover; increasing intrusion of inland sea water, decreasing groundwater and surface water discharge, increasing traffic concentration which results in traffic jams; increasing number of critical lands; decreasing level of regional facilities and infrastructure services; social problems, population and employment; as well as the fading of cultural values as markers of the identity of the Balinese people and region.

The main issue in regional development at the moment is that there are still large gaps between regions, especially the development gap between Southern Bali and North Bali, East and West. In this regard, the main policy direction for provincial regional development is focused on accelerating the reduction of development gaps between regions. Therefore, a regional development direction is needed that can encourage transformation and acceleration of regional development. Bali has an economic style that is slightly different from other regions. The supporting capacity of the agricultural, tourism and tourism supporting services sectors is the basic capital in driving development in the Province of Bali.

Data shows that more than 60% of Bali's economic activity is contributed by the tourism industry, while the contribution from the agricultural sector is no more than 20%.

5. DISCUSSION

Development/development of the Bali economy in accordance with regional potential in order to balance the centers of economic growth between regions throughout Bali, thereby increasing economic growth, increasing regional income, opening new jobs, and reducing poverty levels.

Bali's economic transformation policy is strengthened by the Kerthi Bali Economic concept, namely a comprehensive economic concept to realize Bali Independence in the Economic Sector, built and developed based on the values of the Sad Kerthi philosophy. Kerthi Bali's Six Leading Economic Sectors as Pillars of the Bali Economy, include: 1) Agricultural Sector; 2) Marine/Fisheries Sector; 3) Industrial Sector; 4) SME, MSME and Cooperative Sector; 5) Creative and Digital Economy Sector; and 6) Tourism Sector.

Bali for 2018-2023 is similar to the vision and mission stated in the RPJPD Semesta Plan for Bali Province for 2005-2023. The vision of the RPJPD Semesta Plan for Bali Province for 2005-2025 is "NANGUN SAT KERTHI LOKA BALI" through the Universal Planned Development Pattern. This vision contains the meaning of maintaining the purity and harmony of Balinese nature and its contents, to realize a prosperous and happy Balinese Krama life, Sakala-Niskala towards Balinese Krama and Gumi life in accordance with Bung Karno's Trisakti Principles: Politically Sovereign, Economically Independent, and Deeply Personal. Culture Through Patterned, Comprehensive, Planned, Directed and Integrated Development Within the Frame of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia Based on the Values of Pancasila 1 June 1945.

6. CONCLUSION

Bali as a world tourist destination is currently developing village tourism as a unique tourist destination. Apart from creating popular tourism, it is also believed to be a form of cultural communication for Balinese tourism which is based on cultural tourism. A number of suggestions that need to be conveyed are to the provincial/regency and city governments to focus more on what is stipulated in the tourism village policy. Programs developed to be more focused on achieving the vision and mission of regional tourism development. To the tourist village, to better coordinate the tourist village development program with various parties so that the objectives of establishing a tourist village can be realized. This condition is based on the large number of tourist villages that have not taken further action after being designated as tourist villages.

Reference

- 1) Airey, D. (1983). European government approaches to tourism. *Tourism Management*, 4(4), 234-244.
- 2) Azcairate, M. C. (2006). Between Local and Global, Discourses and Practices: Rethinking Ecotourism Development in Celestan (Yucatan, Mexico). *Journal of Ecotourism*, 5(1/2), 97-111.
- 3) Baum, T. (1994). The development and implementation of national tourism policies. *Tourism Management*, 15(3), 185-192.
- 4) Dredge, D., & Jenkins, J. (2007). *Tourism Planning and Policy*. Brisbane: John Wiley and Sons.
- 5) Fayos-Sola, E. (1992a). A strategic outlook for regional tourism policy. *Tourism Management*, 13(1), 45-49.
- 6) Hall, C. M. (2000). *Tourism Planning: Policies, Processes and Relationships*. Harlow: Pearson Education.
- 7) Harrison, D., & Schipani, S. (2007). Lao Tourism and Poverty Alleviation: Community-Based Tourism and the Private Sector. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 10(2/3), 194-230.

- 8) Jafari, J. (1989). An English-language literature review. In J. Bystrzanowski (Ed.), *Tourism as a factor of change: the sociocultural study* (pp. 17-60). Vienna: Centre for Research and Documentation in Social Sciences.
- 9) Jenkins, C. L., & Henry, B. M. (1982). Government involvement in tourism in developing countries. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 9(4), 499-521.
- 10) Jenkins, J. (2001). Editorial. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 4(2), 69 - 77.
- 11) Kerr, W. (2003). *Tourism Public Policy, and the strategic Management of Failure*. New York: Pergamon.
- 12) Sharpley, R., & Telfer, D. J. (2002). *Tourism and Development : Concepts and Issues*. Buffalo: Multilingual Matters.
- 13) Stevenson, N., Airey, D., & Miller, G. (2008). Tourism Policy Making: The Policymakers' Perspectives. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 35(3), 732-750.
- 14) Van Doorn, J. W. M. (1982). Can Futures Research Contribute to Tourism Policy. *Tourism Management*, 3(3), 149-166.